

**REPORT ON TECHNOLOGICAL
VALIDATION RESULTS, EFFECTIVENESS
OF EACH VALIDATED INNOVATIVE
SYSTEM, PROCESS, AND TOOL, AND
DESCRIPTION OF THE FOODLAND NEW
FOOD PRODUCTS**

D5.17

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Short Description
<p>This report summarizes the main results obtained from the development, test and validation of the FoodLAND innovations including new systems, processes and tools, as well as new food products. While the realized innovation activities, results and impacts are described in detail by the series of relevant deliverables (prototypes and protocols), this report provides an overview of the project R&I achievements by adopting the impact pathway approach, thus focusing on their main outputs, outcomes and impacts. This overall description is then integrated with final considerations on the lessons learned from the conducted R&I activities, on policy implications and future research needs.</p>

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1. Introduction

1.1 Prototype motivations, general objectives and targets

The context of the African food systems and the problems/users' needs the project open prototypes have addressed, their general objectives and main targets (with special attention to gender issues).

The development and validation of open prototypes, including 23 technological innovations and 26 new food products, have been motivated by the need to enhance opportunities for food operators and food security. Within the broader context of African food systems, these prototypes address key challenges affecting both the supply chains and the consumers' conditions. On the one hand lack of coordination among smallholder farmers, inefficient use of resources, high vulnerability to climate change, low integration of supply chains, and scarce market orientation often characterize the local food systems. On the other hand population suffers from different forms of malnutrition and limited access to nutrient-rich foods. The conducted R&I activities and the realized prototypes contribute to boosting both the nutrition-responsiveness of the local food chains and the dietary healthiness, thus closing the gap between operators and consumers.

Moving from this overall objective, the FoodLAND prototypes strengthen local food systems by valorising indigenous available varieties and species, and promoting sustainable and resilient agricultural and processing practices, while creating affordable, nutrient-dense food products tailored to the dietary and economic needs of the local communities.

The main targets are smallholder farmers and SMEs, as well as rural and peri-urban populations, particularly women and children as groups most vulnerable to dietary deficiencies, identified in selected 14 (rural and peri-urban) Food Hubs paired with 14 separate cities across 6 African countries. Special attention is given to gender inclusivity by empowering rural women as key operators in production and dissemination, fostering economic independence and improving household nutrition.

While the project successfully achieved all planned objectives and expected results, a few minor deviations were encountered—none of which represent significant departures from the Document of Action. These include a relatively modest level of policy engagement and limited integration of project outputs into institutional frameworks, as well as the non-implementation of the precision harvesting system in two of the five targeted Food Hubs.

With regard to contribution of the innovations to the improvement of the nutrition performance of the local food systems, it must be considered that process innovations aimed to improve the farming and food processing activities producing conventional foods are expected to broadly improve food security by increasing yield and reducing losses (as measured by the KPIs reported the relevant deliverables). In these circumstances, no dedicated analyses of nutrition performance were conducted. On the contrary, when product innovations were developed the validation included the characterization of the nutrition properties of the realized new foods as reported in D5.16 (Report on the functional and nutritional properties of the validated FOODLAND novel food products).

Finally, by design, the project developed, implemented and validated open prototypes in the relevant environment—specifically up to Technology Readiness Level 5 (TRL5). As such, activities beyond this scope, including the scaling-up of technological innovations, assessment of market viability, and measurement of nutritional impact on the population, were deliberately excluded from the project objectives.

2. FoodLAND open technological innovations and new food products

This section provides a comprehensive overview of the realized technological innovations (new method / system / tools) and new food products as result of the testing phase in lab / at small-scale level (WP4) and feedback gathered from the field innovation validation (WP5).

According to the impact pathway approach, the achieved R&I outputs (publications) and outcomes, and the main generated impacts are described.

Table 1. – Food Hubs, open innovations, and target food products and cities.

Food Hub	Open technological innovation			New food product <i>(italic)</i>	City
	Farming	Primary processing	Secondary processing		
1. Zoyout Dir Beni Mellal / Khenifra	Precision harvesting	–	Centrifugation, filtration, clarification. Labelling	<i>Extra virgin and virgin olive oil.</i>	Beni Mellal (MA)
2. Ait Ouallal Bittit / Ait Yazem	Precision protection and irrigation	Smart storage	–	Fresh vegetables, potatoes, onions.	Meknès (MA)
3. Enfidha, Chebika	Biodegradable mulching	Milling	Baking	Fresh vegetables, legumes. <i>Two composite flours (cereals, legumes, vegetables). Cookies. Energetic bars.</i>	Sousse (TN)
4. Jendouba	Community gardening. Hydroponic system. Integrated aquaculture	Osmotic dehydration. Solar air drying	Packaging	Fresh fruits, vegetables and legumes. <i>Dried vegetables. Dried fish.</i>	Tunis (TN)
5. Laelay Machew / Axum	Precision harvesting	Smart storage Milling	Packaging Labelling	<i>Composite flour (teff, moringa).</i>	Mekelle (ET)
6. Akaki, Nifas Silk	Peri-urban hydroponics	–	–	Fresh vegetables, legumes	Addis Ababa (ET)
7. Mukurweini	Precision harvesting	Smart storage Solar drying	Juicing, extraction,	<i>Therapeutic powder (tree tomato).</i>	Nyeri (KE)

			fortification. Packaging	<i>Therapeutic juice (tree tomato).</i> Dried fruits, cereals.	
8. Kitui	Precision harvesting	Smart storage Solar drying Milling	Juicing, extraction, fortification. Extrusion, Baking Packaging	<i>Baby food (cereal-based).</i> Dried fruits, vegetables, and legumes.	Kitui (KE)
9. Kisumu	Peri-urban integrated aquaculture	–	–	Fish	Kisumu (KE)
10. Mvomero, Morogoro rural	Selection of new lines Intercropping Precision harvesting	Smart storage Milling	Packaging	<i>Four legume lines. Composite flour (legumes, cereals).</i>	Morogoro (TZ)
11. Kilombero / Lindi	Rural aquaculture Intercropping	Smart storage Solar drying	Packaging	Dried vegetables and fish	Dar es Salaam (TZ)
12. Kamuli	Agro-ecological intensification	Smart storage Milling	Extrusion Baking	<i>Composite flour (legumes, cereals). Snack (legumes, cereals). Noodles.</i>	Kalerwe (UG)
13. Nakaseke	Precision fertigation and harvesting	Solar drying	Packaging	Fresh and dried fruits and vegetables. <i>Bean sauce. Amaranth-enriched wheat.</i>	Kapeeka (UG)
14. Kajjansi / Masaka	Rural aquaculture and polyculture	Solar drying. Milling. Smoking, salting, fermenting	Smoking, salting, fermenting; Extrusion, Baking Packaging	<i>Dried fish. Fish powder. Fish oils. Fish cakes and crackers. Fish balls, noodles, nuggets, burgers, fillets.</i>	Kampala (UG)

2.1 Summary of the R&I outputs

Table 2. – Research articles: published, submitted, working papers.

Field of activity	Type of R&I open innovation (new technology / system / tool / food product)	Output: n. of publications
Background research	Consumer studies	24
	Farmer studies	23
Farming	New improved legume lines	2
	Agro-ecological intensification and biodegradable mulching	4
	Community gardening and hydroponic systems	2
	Precision irrigation / fertigation systems	5
	Precision protection systems	1
	Precision harvesting systems	-
	Integrated aquaculture systems	2
	Smart storage systems	3
Primary processing	Drying systems, Milling, Fish smoking, salting, and fermenting	3
Secondary processing	Centrifugation, filtration, and clarification; Juicing, extraction, and fortification; Extrusion and baking	1
	Bio-based packaging	8
	Characterization and labelling; Marketing tests	6
	New food raw materials and ingredients	4
	New food products	4
Total		92

The table does not include conference abstracts / proceedings / posters, communication articles, news items, ...

The list of research articles provided with DOI is reported in deliverable D6.1 – Databank.

2.2 Summary of the R&I outcomes

Table 3. – Number of food operator innovators involved in the validation activities (WP5).

Food chain segment	Type of R&I open innovation (new technology / system / tool / food product)	Innovators: farmers / SMEs (n.)
Farming	New improved legume lines	200
	Agro-ecological intensification and biodegradable mulching	164
	Community gardening and hydroponic systems	181
	Precision irrigation / fertigation systems	474
	Precision protection systems	400
	Precision harvesting systems	674
	Integrated aquaculture systems	250 / 11
	Smart storage systems	513 / 1
Primary processing	Drying systems	107 / 1
	Milling	718 / 6
	Fish smoking, salting, and fermenting	30 / 2
Secondary processing	Bio-based packaging	68 / 7
	New food raw materials and ingredients	723 / 11
	New food products	287 / 7 / 302 street vendors

Table 4. – Farmer and SME innovators and population per Food Hub.

Food Hub	Innovators: farmers / SMEs (n.)	Farmer population (n.)
1. Zoyout Dir Beni Mellal / Khenifra (MA)	400	600
2. Ait Ouallal Bittit / Ait Yazem (MA)	430	1,200
3. Enfidha, Chebika (TN)	85 / 6	13,675
4. Jendouba (TN)	101 / 8	290,000
5. Laelay Machew / Axum (ET)	834 / 1	17,119
6. Akaki, Nifas Silk (ET)	120	1,014
7. Mukurweini (KE)	177	3,471
8. Kitui (KE)	181 / 2	878
9. Kisumu (KE)	90	2,027
10. Mvomero, Morogoro rural (TZ)	392 / 4	260,504
11. Kilombero / Lindi (TZ)	90	2,610
12. Kamuli (UG)	100 / 3	59,000
13. Nakaseke (UG)	193 / 6	25,000
14. Kajjansi / Masaka (UG)	138 / 20	11,000

2.3 Summary of the R&I impacts

Table 5. – Main impacts (technology, production, nutrition) per type of innovation.

Type of open innovation (new technology / system / tool / food product)	Main impacts	Prototype and Protocol description (Deliverable n.)
New improved legume lines	Improved traits (Fe, Zn, fibre) and yield	D5.2
Agro-ecological and biodegradable mulching	Reduced input use (herbicide, water). Increased yield	D5.3
Community gardening and hydroponic systems	Reduced soil and water use. Increased yield	D5.4
Precision irrigation / fertigation systems	Reduced water use. Increased yield and income	D5.5
Precision protection systems	Reduced phytosanitary products use and losses. Increased income	D5.6
Precision harvesting systems	Reduced losses. Increased income	D5.7
Integrated aquaculture systems	Abated losses during transport. Increased fish yield. Diversified products	D5.8
Smart storage systems	Reduced losses. Increased income	D5.9
Drying systems	Optimised energy and time use. Preserved / increased food quality. Enhanced value-added	D5.10
Milling	Improved shelf life and nutrition retention. Reduced losses. Created new high-quality products. Increased income	D5.10
Fish smoking, salting, and fermenting	Reduced losses. Increased income	D5.10
Centrifugation, filtration, and clarification	Increased healthy and sensory properties, and income. Reduced losses.	D5.12
Juicing, extraction, and fortification	Increased income and micronutrient intake. Decreased random blood sugar.	D5.12

Extrusion and baking	Improved environmental and nutrition scores.	D5.12
Bio-based packaging	By-products and waste valorised. CO2 reduced. Shelf life extended. Nutritional quality preserved/improved.	D5.13
New food raw materials and ingredients	Improved technological properties (e.g., shorter cooking time, higher water absorption capacity and solubility); high content of minerals, vitamins and phytochemicals; good sensorial properties.	D5.11, D.5.16
New food products	Nutritionally enriched compared to benchmarks (e.g., higher fibre, protein and bioactive compounds content); high antioxidant properties; good sensorial properties and high consumer acceptance.	D.514, D5.16

The specific impacts relevant for each validated prototype (technological innovations and new food products) are reported in the mentioned relevant deliverables Prototypes and protocols (from D5.2 to D5.16).

3. Final considerations

General conclusions and evaluations including practice considerations (organizational, operational, technological) on the conducted R&I activities, policy implications, and future research needs and way forward.

The project open prototypes jointly realized by researchers from different disciplines, NGOs and food operators, and implemented in diversified situational conditions by the network of Food Hubs, generated a wealth of experiences relevant for operators, policy makers and the scientific community. While specific conclusions have been derived for each prototype and reported in the dedicated deliverables (from D5.2 to D5.14), this section includes some general considerations and recommendations focused on the main challenges and opportunities to be considered for enhancing the innovation development and diffusion, the smallholder farmers' and SMEs' well-being, and the consumers' quality of life.

3.1 R&I lessons learned: research and practice implication

- The innovations should be jointly identified and developed with the local operators and communities through participatory approaches so as to meet their needs, to ensure alignment with cultural preferences and practical applicability to their daily lives, and to encompass the improvement of entrenched technologies and practices.
- Ad hoc training programs for local operators and especially rural women must be appropriately organized (e.g., through active learning patterns) together with adequate structures and facilities.
- Development of innovations should focus on local varieties and species (with preferred traits) capable to valorise the abundance of biodiversity, food culture, typicality and identity of the African food systems, and to meet nutritional needs.
- Longitudinal research should be implemented for continuous profiling operators' and consumers' needs and preferences, monitoring of situational conditions, technologies efficiency and medium/long-term impacts, thus improving data collection and quality and decision-making data-driven decision-making,
- Inter and transdisciplinary scientific collaboration and stakeholder engagement are essential elements of R&I design and implementation (also considering integration with off-farm income generating activities).

- Smallholder farmers and SMEs should represent the main target of the R&I processes both for social, economic, environmental reasons and for boosting local empowerment, thus implying to give priority to context-specific, affordable, sustainable and replicable innovations.
- Innovations must be based on viable and realistic plans (e.g., advertising sizeable returns to investments should be avoided), whereas involvement of large groups of farmers is likely to be beneficial (spreading risk) and should be favoured.
- With regard to types of innovations, low-risk, process-oriented, short-term effective, and affordable new technologies and systems should be prioritised.
- Innovations addressing medium/long-term challenges (e.g., food shortage and nutritional, health issues) are more likely to be adopted in areas where the related setbacks have been experienced or are expected and by female farmers.
- Innovations enhancing labour productivity, saving resources (seeds, fertilizers), boosting cash rather than subsistence crops (with impact on farm sales and resulting income and on food security) and drought resistant varieties, reducing losses (on field and post-harvest), and ensuring food security should be prioritised.
- Innovations and extension messages should be tailored to different areas and different groups of smallholder farmers, for instance by considering the following pioneers: farmers either belonging to areas affected by issues addressed by the envisaged innovation; farmers managing relatively large farms or having a high household income; young farmers (with variable gender differences); farmers with high levels of trust and risk-taking propensity.
- Characterization of newly developed ingredients and food products as well as wide consumer tests should be carried out to ensure the efficiency of the scale up of the processing conditions tested at lab/pilot scale, to assess the acceptability of the products, and to fill the identified nutritional gaps.
- Performance, production scalability and cost-effectiveness of prototypes of bio-based packaging materials should be implemented, to facilitate their large-scale production and adoption in the food sector and to valorize local agricultural by-products.
- Establishing product specifications for the geographical indication (GI) protection of food items (e.g., extra virgin olive oil and teff flour) in line with European regulations would imply the organization of stakeholders' group/consortium to ensure quality characteristics and standards along the supply chain consistent with the product specification. Further

investigation of specific quality parameters (e.g., such as peroxide value, pungent, and bitter intensities) is required.

3.2 Policy implications

- Local environmental, nutrition and market conditions (e.g., food consumption and shortage and price trends especially in the rural areas) should be continuously monitored to properly define public strategies and interventions.
- Governments and policy-makers must create environments that encourage innovation at all stages (research, development, and commercialization). This can include investing in R&D, providing funding for pilot projects and their scalability, offering tax incentives or subsidies for centres working on sustainable food innovations, and promoting public-private partnerships (PPPs) to bridge the gap between research institutions and operators.
- Innovation should be combined with incentives: local producers' engagement with innovations should be encouraged through public direct payments schemes (e.g., individual, time-limited, small monetary incentives; tax credits or exemptions).
- Specific supporting measures should be introduced/enhanced to boost women's empowerment (e.g., direct deposits, mobile payments, and commitment savings accounts).
- Local inclusive organisations (farmers' associations, cooperatives and groups) and formula for sharing logistic, equipment/machinery, market facilities should be supported and incentives to farmers' (especially women's) membership ensured.
- Role of intermediate bodies (extension services, NGOs, public bodies) in knowledge transfer and dissemination should be enhanced with attention paid to gender inequality.
- Agricultural shows of new agricultural/aquaculture technologies should be introduced at appropriate level so that farmers can affordably participate and get chance to actively exchange experiences.
- Policies should focus on reducing barriers to entry for small-scale producers (especially in favour of young farmers), e.g., land accessibility and inputs (e.g., seed, feed, fertilizers, machines, energy) affordability should be supported, and infrastructures (including internet connectivity) and distribution channels that connect rural producers with urban and regional market improved.

- Economic mechanisms to safeguard poorer farmers (supports, compensations) and avoid the gap between different areas from widening should be introduced.
- Support for credit accessibility and risk-mitigation measures (e.g., mutuality between local farmer groups such as the FoodLAND Food Hubs): balanced mix that spreads risk by combining formal loan, informal credit, and the investment of remittances should be encouraged; farmer-friendly interest rates and smoothed borrowing procedures should be implemented.
- Community and anti-rural poverty social measures: educational and literacy programs, social assistance and programs (also to enhance trust), lifelong training programs, dissemination plans should be adopted/reinforced.
- Regulations for sustainable farming and processing, circular economy principles and standards, certification frameworks and food safety should be implemented/reinforced.
- Tailored nutritional recommendations and campaigns targeting (both male and female) consumers and rural communities and aiming to raise their dietary diversity awareness (e.g., promoting neglected and new food items, lowering the consumption of unhealthy foods and beverages) should be planned and financed.
- Consumption of local, nutrient-dense foods should be promoted by public economic measures.
- Climate change-focused campaigns targeting farmers and rural communities and aiming to raise their environmental awareness should be planned as well.

